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Review Article

To Study the Formulation and Evaluation Parameters of the Solid Perfume Stick (by Using Solidifying Agent and Sandalwood-Rose Oil)

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ABSTRACT

Cosmetic products are mostly used in this modern lifestyle. In the cosmetic products usually perfumes are mostly used for maintain hygiene and personal care . It is useful for attraction of fragrance . Solid perfume stick is a solid balm form also stick or tube container . Solid perfume stick is a vast advanced perfume type to develop new fragrance or scent . The main target of the solid perfume stick is to effectively formulate modern perfume with multiple beneficial uses. Solid perfume stick also known as unguent. Solid perfume stick is alcohol free and convenience to all . The solid perfume stick is long lasting perfume type as compare to liquid perfume . It is also convenient for travelling. Use carnauba wax as a solidifying agent for stability of the solid perfume in various temperature. This fragrance is Woody and floral type of solid perfume.

INTRODUCTION

Solid perfume is used for the unpleasant smell from body . This unwanted smell because of the sweat and bacteria on the skin . This bacteria are breaks down the acids in the sweat .

How does sweat gland produce unpleasant odour on the skin??

Sweat and sweating gland

In the human body there are three to four million sweat glands. In the sweat glands there are mainly 2 types :

Eccrine Gland:

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It is simple sweat gland , located in all areas of the skin. In our skin when body temperature rises then these gland release sweat . The main role of the these gland is thermoregulation through evaporative cooling. This gland also help to ji ji , as sweat removes waste products like urea , ammonia and Salt from the body . It also responsible for regulate the body temperature.

Apocrine Gland:

This gland are located in breast, genital area, armpits and eyelids . This gland are produce sweat they produce high in protein which bacteria break down easily. Apocrine gland produce lots of odour from sweat.

What Is Solid Perfume Stick ?

Solid perfume stick also known as perfume balm or deodorant stick. Solid perfume stick is formulated by the natural bees waxes, Shea Butter , cocoa butter, various oils and fragrances, etc. Solid Perfume stick is a vast advanced perfume to develop a new fragrance or scent . Solid perfume is a straight forward as using traditional perfume fragrance. Solid perfume smell good and long-lasting . It also represent positive vibes and increase confidence. This perfume also known as

cream perfume. In the perfume there are numerous number of flavours and fragrances.

Types of solid perfume stick :

1. Oriental solid perfume : cinnamon and ginger
2. Floral Solid Perfume : Jasmine and lavender
3. Fresh Solid Perfume : lemongrass and tea tree
4. Woody Solid Perfume : sandalwood and cedar wood

Requirement Of Solid Perfume stick :

- Uses of solid perfume stick is a effortless as compare to traditional liquid perfume.
- Liquid perfume require alcohol , it evaporate after some time
- In the solid perfume stick uses various natural waxes as a starting point it act as a long lasting
- This perfume stick provide to skin gentle, mild, soothing and non irritating.
- In the liquid perfume it chance to leakage but solid perfume stick it does not leakage

- Liquid perfume is a traditional but solid perfume stick is a vast advanced perfume.

Late 20th century Solid perfume stick introduced by cosmetic product. In this century focus on the convince, portability, and skin friendly.

History of solid perfume stick :

Beginning in the ancient Egypt (c.3000 BCE 500 BCE) formulate balm by using various bees wax, aromatic pastes and oils

In the Medieval and Renaissance period (500 – 1600 CE) used animal fat , flower extract and herbs. This perfume are does not stick.

In the 18th and 19th century in the France expand the industrial influence about the solid perfume . They develop a Solid Pomades.

Early 20th century in this century lipstick style packaging for the solid perfume. This solid perfume more travel friendly than liquid perfume.

In the 21st century Eco and Niche Revival rise of natural and sustainable perfume. In this century Solid Perfume stick are formulated by various natural waxes, butters and alcohol free.

Benefits Of Solid Perfume stick :

- Solid perfume stick is a skin friendly perfume reducing irritation for sensitive skin type.
- This perfume doesn't leak it can be comfortably travel to anywhere.
- Solid perfume stick contain various natural waxes, butters it perform long lasting fragrance.
- Solid perfume stick is also a moisturizer properties because of bees wax and butter .
- It is eco friendly product due to less packaging and no volatile organic compounds.

How to apply solid perfume?

Where to apply solid perfume stick?

- **In Men**

- Lower jaw and neck
- Shoulder
- Chest
- Inner elbow
- Forearm
- Wrist

- **In women**

- Behind the ears
- Neak
- Shoulder
- Chest
- Below your midriff
- Inner elbow
- Wrist
- Behind your knee
- Calves
- Ankles

Purpose of solid perfume stick :

- To maintain personal care and hygiene .
- It is alcohol free , non irritating and travel anywhere.
- This solid perfume is best option for sensitive skin.

- This perfume contain natural waxes , butters and organic ingredients.
- Solid perfume is long lasting fragrance.
- This long lasting fragrance provide positive vibes and increase confidence.
- This perfume help to reduce stress.

Ingredients used to formulate solid perfume stick :

1.Bees wax :

Bees wax is the mostly main or base ingredient in the solid perfume. Bees wax are in solid form. It give structure, helping to mix and hold the fragrance in the solid form perfume. It also gives stability and smooth texture. Bees wax are natural and skin friendly. It is non toxic, natural and non irritating. Bees wax are natural emulsifier and skin protector, since it provide moisturizing benefits.

2. Carnauba wax:

Carnauba wax has a high melting point (82°-86°c) . It does not melt easily. Carnauba wax is used in solid perfume because it provides structure, stability , long lasting and heat stable product. At high temperature, solid perfume are melts easily, but carnauba wax prevent it from melting. In the solid perfume carnauba wax use as a solidifying agent so it holds its structure at high temperature.

3. Sandalwood oil:

Sandalwood oil is mostly used in perfume for fragrance. Sandalwood oil has woody type of fragrance. Sandalwood essential oil is a last longer on the skin. It provide smooth and warm scent. It has skin softening and moturizing property. It is suitable for directly application to the skin. It is non irritating. It's aromatherapeutic benefits can helps to reduce anxiety, promote focus and increase relaxation.

4. Rose oil

Rose oil is an essential oil extracted from a Rose petals. Rose oil has a floral type of fragrance. In

the rose essential oil has a romantic aroma . It provides a long lasting fragrance in the solid perfume. In the rose oil has aromatherapeutic benefits used for stress relieving, anti anxiety and emotionally balancing effect. Rose oil gives pleasant scent in the solid perfume. Rose oil helps to decrease the evaporation rate in solid perfume.

5. Vitamin E

Vitamin E is a additional ingredient used in solid perfume. Vitamin E has natural antioxidant property. It helps to moisturize the skin . It helps to increase shelf life of the product.

Evaluation Parameter:

Evaluation Parameter are studied to check the quality, stability and performance.

1. Organoleptic Evaluation:

- Appearance: To study the colour and uniformity of the solid perfume.
- Odour: To check the fragrance intensity of the product.
- Texture: To check smoothness.
- Spreadability: To study Spreadability on the skin.

2. Physicochemi Evaluation:

- a) Melting Point: To check the melting point of the product in room temperature.
- b) pH: Study the pH to ensure quality and safety of the product.
- c) Volatility: To check the longevity of the solid perfume.
- d) Packaging Compatibility: To ensure that the product and packaging material are do not react with each other.

3. Stability Study: The stability Parameter study to ensure the quality, safety and self-life of the product.

4. Safety Evaluation: In this evaluation the product should be non-irritating and compatibility with the skin.

CONCLUSION:

Solid perfume is a modern perfume type. It is a advanced and useful product for unisex. Solid perfume stick is useful for personal care and hygiene. It is a long-lasting fragrance, travel to anywhere and alcohol-free product. It is a skin friendly product. In this solid perfume use natural waxes i.e. bees wax, carnauba wax, sandalwood and rose oil and vitamin E oil helps for moturizing skin. This article especially different because of carnauba wax, this wax are used as solidifying agent to maintain the melts the solid perfume at high temperature. This wax has a high melting point. The evaluation parameter are studied for quality, safety and stability of the solid perfume.

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